

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Living and Working Conditions of migrant seasonal workers in agriculture in Germany

Sector report

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Executive Summary

This report presents the overview of the key findings from Work Package 5 within the larger research project I-CLAIM: Improving the Living and Labour Conditions of Irregularised Migrant Households in Europe, specifically focusing on the working conditions of migrant seasonal workers in the agricultural sector in Germany. It provides the contextual analysis of migrant labour within this sector, highlighting the challenges and dynamics faced by workers. Additionally, the report explores the living experiences of migrant workers in rural and agricultural settings, offering insights into their working environments. The report also reflects on the ethnographic methodology applied in this research, providing a description of the issues faced.

The ethnographic study reveals that irregularities in the German agricultural sector manifest through semi-formal agreements, oral contracts, and other non-standard forms of employment that bind workers to employers' promises. These forms of irregularities exploit workers' educational disparities and financial insecurity, creating a high level of dependency. This dependency is further exacerbated by substandard housing provided on the farms. Additionally, there is a lack of occupational safety and health protection, as well as a constant linguistic dependency on the employer regarding access to healthcare in the event of illness or accidents. The case study presented in this research, conducted on a farm in the Brandenburg region, illustrates the labour law-violating conditions under which EU-citizens are employed in agriculture.

1. Introduction

The ethnographic research was conducted over a period of nine months (September 2024 to May 2025) and includes expert interviews and interviews with migrant seasonal workers at one farm within the region of Brandenburg. The findings of the research point to an exploitation of lower-income families from EU-countries. In the German agricultural sector close to 30% of the workforce is represented by seasonal workers (next to the majority of workforce employed as family labour), mostly from eastern European States (e.g. Poland and Romania) (Danilova, 2025). Although there is a general downward trend in overall numbers of seasonal workers in Germany, farmers continue to face a persistently high workload, which increasingly challenges their physical and organizational capacity to manage farm operations efficiently. As of January 1, 2025, the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) includes a new requirement known as social conditionality, based on Article 14 of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115. This means that in order to receive full agricultural subsidies, farmers must now also comply with certain labour and social protection standards. Non-compliance with these labour-related rules – such as violations of worker rights, health and safety, or fair treatment – can result in administrative penalties, including reductions in CAP payments. While the new social conditionality aims to improve labour conditions, the practical realities of enforcement and monitoring remain unclear.

This study gives a comprehensive overview of the situation of migrant seasonal workers in Germany, drawing from 6 expert interviews with lawyers, researchers, farmers and various migration labour rights advocates. The ethnographic material gathered in the surroundings of Brandenburg includes 18 interviews with migrant seasonal workers as well as in-depth participant observation, capturing the lived experience of migrant workers in the agricultural sector of Germany. The difficulty of methodologically accessing this field of research is, in itself, evidence of the highly sensitive topic of tolerated labour exploitation and precarious working conditions to which migrant labourers are exposed. The findings account for a systematic labour exploitation of EU-citizens, who live below the poverty line, come from low-income families and are affected by social inequalities and racialisation, which particularly applies to groups such as Roma and Sinti. Due to their precarious living conditions, these migrant workers often feel compelled to accept substandard working conditions in Germany. In addition, employers take advantage of foreign workers' unfamiliarity with legal working conditions in Germany. The result is an employment relationship that is characterised by extreme dependency and existential fears and worries.

2. Context

Most of the seasonal workers in Germany come from EU-States such as Poland, Romania, Hungary and Bulgaria, third-country nationals are rare and often come through bilateral country agreements or via student visas (e.g. Ukrainian, Moldova, Georgia, Kazakhstan) (Wagner and Hassel, 2017). Since the outbreak of the Ukraine-Russia war numbers of Ukrainian migrant seasonal workers significantly diminished as Ukrainians are entitled to state protection and benefits.

Most common contract forms are either short-term employment in the case of EU-citizens or vacation employment for students as well as quota-based employment for workers from countries who have bilateral agreements with Germany. Yet, in practice, the conditions outlined in employment contracts frequently diverge from reality, particularly with regard to the actual number of hours worked. This is the most frequent form of irregularity encountered within contractual agreements in the German agricultural sector. Yet, other forms of exploitation and inadequate labour conditions are known such as working below minimum wage, inadequate housing conditions and a lack of security at workplaces. In 2021, 18 Georgian seasonal workers,

who were employed on the base of bilateral agreements, initiated legal proceedings in Germany, marking the largest labour law dispute in the agricultural sector to date. The migrant workers claimed workload and living accommodations did not correspond with the contractual agreements. Their efforts to claim their rights was assisted by the German migrant NGO *mira – Mit Recht bei der Arbeit*. After three and a half years the case is still unsettled.

Generally, seasonal workers who are recruited through bilateral agreements are often employed under better conditions than those who are hired directly by farmers or through informal intermediaries. Migrant workers who come through bilateral agreements have a better legal base to claim rights, as they are able to refer to contractual agreements. In contrast, migrants who are hired by farmers or through intermediaries often lack knowledge about their rights and how to assert them. Illiteracy is particularly prevalent among Romanian workers who belong to the group of Roma and Sinti. Therefore, many contracts resemble a kind of blank check: migrants sign them without knowing what conditions the employer will include or may later change. As contracts are exclusively in German almost all the migrants had to rely on oral information on their work terms and conditions. Furthermore, they have to trust that the employment terms promised to them are in fact recorded in their employment contract. Often, contracts are not handed over to the workers, making it difficult for them to refer to, or enforce their rights.

The majority of seasonal workers migrate with the primary objective of increasing their income to support the subsistence of their families in their countries of origin, to which they return upon accumulating sufficient earnings. Money is the primary objective for low-income families. This results in these individuals being particularly vulnerable, as wages are only paid at the end of the season. A dependency relationship develops which can take on coercive forms if employers are dissatisfied and threaten to withhold wages. In Germany short-term employment in agriculture, typically lasting up to 70 days or 3 months per year, is exempt from social security contributions, leaving seasonal workers without health insurance and pension rights. This lack of coverage results in limited access to medical care and the inability to accrue future pension entitlements, contributing to long-term financial insecurity. Workers in such positions often face wage disparities, earning a lower amount than their colleagues. The dependency on temporary, low-wage jobs forces many workers, especially those from vulnerable backgrounds, to accept poor working conditions. This situation exacerbates their vulnerability, as employers can exploit this dependency, in particular since workers live in homes rented out by employers.

“It is already very difficult for us to get in touch with the people, and often they don’t want to testify or assert their claims. Customs only checks paperwork, and it is mostly accurate. The living conditions are not checked, even though people are living in barracks, four in a room of 8m². The public prosecutor is often informed, but no one wants to testify because they want to return to work.”

This statement by a migrant rights advocate illustrates the situation of seasonal agricultural workers in Germany. Despite efforts to inform and support migrants about their entitlements and labour rights, the barriers to accessing the remote group of migrant workers render activists and trade union endeavours difficult. Even when access to the group is reached, the fear of losing their jobs and thus their livelihoods often hinder any legal measures against labour exploitation in agriculture as migrants refuse to testify in front of court or police. Moreover, this statement points to the lack of state regulation in appointing authorities that ensure that the regulation for social conditionality is met. In Germany, there exists no authority that monitors occupational safety in the workplace. Occupational safety falls under the jurisdiction

of the customs authorities, which only become active when there are indications of financial or tax-related violations. As the person above describes, the German customs authority is only responsible for compliance with tax-relevant circumstances and seldom monitor living and working conditions on farms and fields which according to experts are degrading.

Ultimately, the combination of precarious employment and lack of social security fuels a cycle of exploitation and poverty for seasonal workers and their families (Fiałkowska and Matuszczyk, 2021). On the other hand, farmers report that rising operational costs, more stringent regulatory requirements, and an increasing workload are significantly influencing the viability and sustainability of agricultural practices.

3. Methodology

Accessing the field proved to be highly challenging due to widespread caution and reluctance from key stakeholders. Both institutional contacts (e.g., farmers' associations and religious communities) and individual actors (e.g., farmers) were either unresponsive, withdrew initial openness, or subtly distanced themselves, reflecting concerns about potential reputational risks. Overall, the topic of migrant agricultural labour appeared to be shrouded in a culture of silence and guardedness, making ethnographic engagement particularly difficult. Reaching the research group – seasonal workers – was particularly challenging due to the remote and rural location of the areas where migrant workers are employed in the agricultural sector. Over the course of the ethnographic research, six formal expert interviews were held with NGOs, trade unions, a lawyer and other actors involved in the theme of agricultural work (see Table I in the Appendix).

The majority of the workers are EU-citizens and therefore have regular residence status; however, they face precarious and exploitative working conditions (Bruzelius and Seeleib-Kaiser, 2023). As they are often unaware of the legal or semi-legal status of their employment terms, they shy away from speaking with NGOs, which function like trade unions, or with other individuals who might play a role in conducting inspections. The language barrier posed a significant challenge as many workers only speak their mother tongue, with Bulgarian, Romanian and Polish being the most commonly used languages. Hence, the Romanian-speaking community researcher employed to support the data collection was a key figure in building trust to the migrant workers. Still suspiciousness was common and some of the migrants refused to talk to us after having listened to the explanation of the research objective or interrupted the interview when inquiries into forms of contract or exploitative issues became very upfront. Likewise, interlocutors stated, “there is so much more things I could tell you, but if I do I can pack my things and leave”. In all interviews, it became very clear that there is an extreme fear of speaking or sharing anything negative about working conditions. This was evident even though we assured interlocutors of complete confidentiality and conducted the interviews away from their workplace. These barriers made effective communication difficult and prevented the researcher from successfully explaining the research objective. In addition, the physically demanding labour of the workers often led to exhaustion during breaks, which further limited their availability and willingness to participate in interviews. This combination of factors led to significant challenges in accessing the field and establishing contact with the research group. All interviews with migrant workers were conducted outside a local supermarket frequented by the participants. In total, eighteen individuals were interviewed – three women and fifteen men, all of Romanian origin, of which 15 belonged to Roma communities (see Table II in the Appendix). Romanians were by far the majority of workers at the farm.

At the time of the field research, the farm primarily cultivated asparagus and strawberries. It operates exclusively on open farmland and has, for many years, relied on seasonal labour due to the extensive size of the areas requiring cultivation. Most interviewees were men. Interviewees explained that gender imbalance at the farm is because women rarely come on their own, meaning that most of the female seasonal workers come with their husband. The use of a voucher as an incentive proved particularly effective and was well-received by participants. However, the interviews were conducted without prior mention of the voucher, as this approach was deemed more appropriate given the general atmosphere of suspicion among potential interviewees for the same reason, interviews were not recorded. Seasonal workers also refused to continue talking when notes were taken during interviews. Moreover, the fact that the Community Researcher and Researcher communicated in English often arose fear and suspicion. Hence, the research team decided to introduce the German researcher as Italian speaking. To ensure that data was saved the researchers recorded the summary of conversations among them after each interview. As trust-building was particularly difficult sensitive individual information were not asked including age and names. The estimated age of interviewees was between 40-60 years, occasionally younger couples between estimated 25-35 years old.

Nevertheless, as word spread within the community that interlocutors were receiving vouchers, an increasing number of individuals began approaching the research team. It became evident that financial compensation was a strong motivating factor for participation. However, the interviews conducted under these circumstances were generally of lower qualitative depth, with participants often providing brief or superficial responses. Through regular visits to the same location, trust relationships were established with some of the migrant workers. In particular, socializing together – drinking and smoking in front of the supermarket, discussing political and family matters, and sharing jokes – played a significant role in fostering positive relationships. As a result, migrants began to exchange contact information with us and even inquired whether they could seek assistance from us regarding their work-related issues if needed. The balance between a female researcher and a male community researcher was helpful in engaging both genders and establishing a more familial rapport. Additionally, since the community researcher had already gained insights and experiences on other farms regarding the lived realities of migrant seasonal workers, helpful comparisons could be drawn. In conclusion, it can be said that conducting the ethnography over a longer period would have significantly benefited relationship building and networking and would have provided deeper insights. The research period chosen for the agricultural ethnography from June 2024 to March 2025 was inconvenient as it mostly run out of seasons. This was confirmed by expert voices who deemed a research period from February to October as the most appropriate in Germany.

4. Main Findings from Ethnography

All data represented here draws from the interviews with migrant workers at a farm in the region of Brandenburg.

4.1. Recruitment and Onboarding Process

The recruitment and onboarding process for seasonal agricultural workers appears to be informal, decentralised, and deeply embedded in existing social networks. A key figure in the process of the respective farm was a Romanian secretary employed at the farm, who facilitated communication by speaking Romanian, Bulgarian, and Polish – an asset that significantly aided newly arrived workers. In addition to the Romanian secretary, a Roma woman played an active role in recruiting labourers, further indicating the importance of community-based channels. Some workers mentioned being dissatisfied with the current

farm owner, with one expressing the desire to “change the owner of the farm”. In several cases, the farm owner personally travelled to Roma villages to recruit workers directly, highlighting the top-down dimension to the process. Other workers reported being recruited through informal means such as word-of-mouth – often through a “friend of a friend” – as well as through banners posted in villages. Given the precarious financial circumstances of all interview participants, it can be inferred that recruitment is systematically carried out in poorer regions or among disadvantaged groups – specifically, among Roma and Sinti communities.

4.2. Work Processes and Labor Conditions

Seasonal workers typically arrive in February and remain for five to eight months. Their working hours are approximately eight to nine hours per day, usually starting at 7 a.m. and ending around 4 p.m. Many workers are paid the minimum wage in Germany, currently €12.80 per hour. However, there is a wage disparity among couples, as one spouse is often socially insured and thus earns the minimum wage, while the other is employed temporarily and registered as a househusband or housewife earning €9 per hour. Wages are generally paid at the end of the season or after the end of three-month contract. However, interlocutors reported that those with longer-standing relationships with the farm were sometimes able to request an advance paycheck, amounting to €300 or more. In general, it was observed that workers who have been coming for a longer period tend to receive higher wages and are accommodated under better living conditions. No work clothing is provided with the exception of work shoes, which the workers are required to purchase for a fee of 20€. Additional equipment like gloves, jackets or work trousers can be requested by workers but have to be paid for. In terms of equipment, workers reported the use of outdated machinery and noted that no significant improvements were made in recent years. Workers’ accounts indicated insufficient compliance with legal regulations concerning occupational safety and the use of machinery, which in some cases has led to workplace accidents. Examples included overloading machines beyond their permitted weight limits or coupling multiple trailers in a manner that violates traffic regulations. The workers expressed frustration over being coerced into unsafe and unlawful tasks under threat of legal or financial consequences, highlighting systemic exploitation and the vulnerability of migrant labour in this context. In this context, one migrant worker belonging to the Roma community stated, “it feels like they teach us how to be civilized and they learned from us how to not be tracked by the law”. The labour environment on the farm is structured through a mix of informal coercion, surveillance, and selective incentives. Workers describe a punitive and reward-based system, where those who work harder or longer are offered extended contracts and slight wage increases – such as a shift from an official three-month contract to a self-employed 9€/hour rate contract – but these terms are not always transparent or consistent.

Surveillance is enforced through peer informants, with one individual acting as a “spy”, reporting conversations to the boss, who in turn issues verbal warnings or threatens exclusion from future employment. Workers are occasionally informed by the Romanian secretary about their tax declarations or possibilities to recover taxes from authorities upon their return in Romania. At the end of employment, “papers” are handed out that confirm a job position at the farm for the next year. However, not all workers receive these papers or are informed about tax recovery possibilities, suggesting blurred legal boundaries. While some are able to record and claim overtime, others – like a Roma worker who never received his contract despite repeated requests – struggle with communication barriers and unfulfilled promises.

In terms of health, only severe illness is formally acknowledged through sick leave, yet payment terms remain unclear. Performance-based pay, such as “more kilos, more money”, coexists with exploitative

conditions, leading many to express disillusionment and likewise to continue working even when experiencing mild symptoms of illness. There exists a similar pressure system among workers, based on the notion that “those who do not work hard will not be invited back next year”. Many of the workers have been returning for multiple seasons, some for as many as 8 to 15 years. Healthcare access on the farm appears minimal and largely dependent on employer discretion. In cases of visible illness, such as severe stomach pain, the employer may offer to take workers to the hospital, although the process lacks transparency. Workers are highly dependent on their employers for access to medical assistance, particularly due to language barriers and limited knowledge of local healthcare facilities. While sick leave is reportedly paid, workers are uncertain about the amount or structure of compensation. Sickness is often managed informally by workers, sourcing basic medicines independently. One worker, comparing the living situation and work conditions to his experience in Italy, declared, “I would change everything here”. Another, who needed to attend a court appointment in Romania, was told he would forfeit his earned wages if he left. Statements like “I’m not in a prison, why is this happening to me?” and “We live like robots” reflect the emotional toll of a monotonous and tightly controlled work regime. Even holiday entitlements remain ambiguous, with some working through Easter without additional compensation, though workers can nominally choose one day off per week.

4.3. Migration status and Living conditions

All interview participants were EU-citizens from Romania as this represented the highest group of seasonal workers at the farm, with most belonging to the Roma and Sinti communities. Over the course of the ethnographic research, it became clear that migrant seasonal workers consistently viewed the cost of living as a significant financial burden. This observation points to a broader pattern of socio-economic marginalisation and structural poverty within the group of seasonal workers. Several interlocutors described their financial precarity, while others expressed a desire for improved living conditions in Romania, stating that such improvements would remove the necessity of migrating to Germany for economic reasons. One worker noted that, in addition to field labour, he regularly collects bottles and cans to redeem deposits, using the funds to buy essential goods such as bread. Mobility in the village and its surroundings remains a challenge, for all migrant workers who don’t come with their own cars, leading some workers to purchase second-hand bicycles from itinerant Polish sellers for around 20€. Seasonal workers typically travel in self-organised groups, often composed of family members or friends, and commonly use private vehicles to travel to Germany for work. Many also reported prior experiences of working in agriculture in other European countries, including Belgium, Italy, and Spain. All seasonal workers reported to travel back home to families after the season.

4.4. Gender and households

At the time of the data gathering period 15 female workers were among the approximately 80 seasonal workers of the farm. According to the interlocutors, the overall number of migrant workers at the farm could reach up to 300 during high season. As interviewees described, female field workers come exclusively with their husbands. As a result, the most common groups among the field workers were young married couples or couples who regularly return as seasonal workers to the farm. Siblings and cousins who have been coming for many years as well often accompany them. In very rare cases, adult children or friends accompany them. Younger children are left with grandparents or other family members back home. This results in a strong male-dominated work environment, which reflected in the interviews as men often took speaking initiative when women were proactively addressed. Usually, friends and families of one household share an

accommodation for the duration of the stay. This results in sometimes two, four or more people sharing a room that is furnished with mattresses, an electric kitchen, a refrigerator, a table and benches. The living conditions of seasonal workers reflect stark inequalities and substandard housing arrangements. Many are accommodated in barracks – former military facilities that have been repurposed as worker housing. For the accommodation, each worker is charged €12 per day, amounting to approximately €360 per month which is deducted directly from their wages. Despite sharing a room, all occupants are required to pay the full amount individually. Interviewees described the conditions as extremely poor, noting, for instance, that some rooms have asphalt floors. Sanitary facilities are shared with separate toilets for men and women; however, these are typically located outside and can be up to five minutes walking distance from the living quarters – posing an inconvenience, especially at night. In contrast, workers in higher-status positions – such as tractor drivers or those with administrative responsibilities – are housed in noticeably better accommodations, highlighting a clear hierarchy within the labour force that is mirrored in their living standards. One interlocutor remarked that he had sent photographs of his living conditions back home, noting that his friends could hardly believe he was actually in Germany – an observation that underscores the severity of the inadequate housing and the dissonance between expectations and reality for migrant workers.

4.5. Racial dimension

Racial and ethnic hierarchies are a visible and deeply felt aspect of life on the farm. Tensions exist not only between workers and management but also among different ethnic groups, with reported hostility and division between Romanian workers and Roma Romanian individuals as well as between different Roma groups, occasionally escalating into threats and the presence of weapons such as knives. A common perception among Romanian workers is that they are collectively devalued by the employer and described dismissively as “just some Romanians”. These dynamics extend beyond the farm itself: when the workers’ water supply failed, local German neighbours reportedly refused to help, indicating broader social exclusion. Within the workplace, Polish workers appear to hold preferential status – occupying less physically demanding roles such as drivers, packers, or managers, enjoying better housing, and generally receiving more favourable treatment. Many attribute this to their earlier arrival within the German agricultural sector, which has translated into entrenched structural advantages. These disparities contribute to a layered system of racialised labour, where opportunities, recognition, and conditions are unevenly distributed along ethnic lines.

4.6. Female Voices

In the male-dominated field of agricultural labour, women are not only underrepresented but also exposed to specific dangers and forms of exploitation. Coercion into relationships with higher-ranking male workers is sometimes perceived as a survival strategy. The expert interviews reported incidents of sexual assault in the agricultural sector in Germany, including two cases of rape by an employer and a co-worker, which were uncovered and legally supported by an NGO. It is likely that such cases are far more frequent than currently assumed, as women have little access to privacy or protective spaces in the working context of agriculture. Isolation and remoteness significantly increase the risk of coercion and abuse going unnoticed.

5. Concluding Remarks

The systematic exploitation of EU-citizens affected by marginalisation and poverty is a defining characteristic of the agricultural sector in Germany. Deficiencies in education and a lack of awareness regarding tax systems and employment regulations hinder migrant workers from escaping exploitative employment relationships. The combination of employer-provided accommodation and end-of-season wage payments creates a pronounced dependency relationship. This is further exacerbated by substandard housing conditions at disproportionately high costs, as well as insufficient occupational health and safety provisions. Female workers are particularly vulnerable to abuse due to inadequate housing arrangements. Irregularity in the German agricultural sector are found in semi-legal and grey-area contractual arrangements, often verbal or not provided to seasonal workers, under which migrants are employed. In addition, there are serious violations of occupational health, safety regulations and working conditions on the part of farmers.

In Germany, efforts to address and inform seasonal workers about their labour rights lay mostly with partially state-funded NGOs. Yet, the unsuccessful but persistent efforts of labour activists in addressing this particular group show little effect on the working and living conditions on farms. Language barriers, remoteness, surveillance, fear and time constraints make endeavours to mobilise with workers particularly challenging. Social fragmentation among workers, and internal divisions significantly impede collective organisation and resistance to exploitative practices. This shows that the barrier in this area is unlike other sectors in Germany. Additionally, a pervasive atmosphere of fear toward authorities and researchers further inhibits the assertion of rights and access to support structures.

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Appendix 1

Table I

Expert Interviews	Gender	Nationality	Institution/Role
1	w	Ukrainian	Trade Union
2	w	Polish	NGO
3	w	German	NGO
4	m	German	farmer
5	w	Romanian	Migrant Advocate
6	w	German	lawyer

Table II

Migrant Interviews	Gender	Nationality	Region	Legal status
1	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
2	m	Romanian	Romanian	Short term
3	m	Romanian	Romanian	Short term
4	w	Romanian	Roma	Short term
5	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
6	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
7	m	Romanian	Romanian	Short term
8	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
9	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
10	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
11	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
12	w	Romanian	Roma	Short term
13	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
14	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
15	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
16	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
17	m	Romanian	Roma	Short term
18	w	Romanian	Roma	Short term

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